

Novel Multinomial Expansion and Theorem

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical and combinatorial equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. This paper presents a new multinomial expansion and theorem. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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Construction of Multinomial Expansion

The novel binomial and multinomial expansions are developed using the binomial coefficients defined in combinatorial geometric series. The combinatorial geometric series and its binomial coefficient are given below:

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient defined in combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem: The following theorem is a new multinomial expansion:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r_1+r_2+r_3+\cdots+r_{k-1}+r_k+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n (n+1-i) V_i^{r_1+r_2+r_3+\cdots+r_{k-1}+r_k}.$$

Proof. This multinomial expansion (multinomial theorem) is proved using the following theorem which has been already proved in the author's previous papers.

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r x^i + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r x^i + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r x^i \quad (\text{theorem}).$$

By substituting $x = 1$ in this theorem, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r.$$

Let $R = r_1 + r_2 + r_3 + \cdots + r_{k-1} + r_k$.

$$\text{Then, } \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{R+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^R + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^R + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^R + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^R + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^R.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^R + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^R + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^R + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^R + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^R \\ = (V_0^R + V_1^R + V_2^R + V_3^R + \cdots + V_n^R) + (V_0^R + V_1^R + V_2^R + V_3^R + \cdots + V_{n-1}^R) \\ + (V_0^R + V_1^R + V_2^R + V_3^R + \cdots + V_{n-1}^R) + \cdots + (V_0^R + V_1^R) + V_0^R. \end{aligned}$$

In this expression, the number of terms $V_0^R, V_1^R, V_2^R, V_3^R, \dots, V_{n-2}^R, V_{n-1}^R$, and V_n^R are $(n+1), n, (n-1), (n-2), \dots, 3, 2$, and 1 respectively. Now, we can conclude that

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{R+1} = (n+1)V_0^R + nV_1^R + (n-1)V_2^R + \cdots + 3V_{(n-2)}^R + 2V_{(n-1)}^R + V_n^R.$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{R+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n (n+1-i)V_i^R,$$

$$i. e. \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r_1+r_2+r_3+\cdots+r_{k-1}+r_k+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n (n+1-i)V_i^{r_1+r_2+r_3+\cdots+r_{k-1}+r_k}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

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